

Cycloaddition approach to five-membered heterocycles – Some recent experimental and theoretical aspects[†]

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Abstract : 1,3-Dipolar cycloaddition reactions of nitrones to substituted olefins give rise to synthetically useful isoxazolidines with up to three new chiral centers. The preferred regio- and stereochemical mode of approach of the dipolarophile over the dipole controls the selectivities of such reactions. These can be rationalised by DFT based theoretical models in terms of reactivity indices, interaction energies and the activation parameters. A short review of some recent experimental and theoretical aspects of these cycloadditions is presented.

Keywords : Nitrones, 1,3-dipolar cycloadditions, DFT calculations.

1. Introduction

1,3-Dipoles are π -electron systems [three atom four electron systems with a central heteroatom (usually oxygen, nitrogen or sulphur)] comprising an empty π -orbital along with two occupied π -orbitals. Being isoelectronic with allyl or propargyl anions, these can be represented by charge separated canonical structures with opposite charges in a 1,3-relationship (Scheme 1).

Smith¹ was the first to present in 1938 a detailed review on the synthesis, structures and reactions of 1,3-dipoles. Rolf Huisgen and his research group carried out extensive work on different aspects of chemistry of 1,3-dipoles in the 1960s and 1970s, laying a solid experimental base for future investigators to build upon². Cycloaddition reactions of different 1,3-dipolar species to double and triple bonds provide a direct synthetic access to stereochemically defined five-membered heterocycles

Scheme 1. 1,3-Dipolar species of nitrones, azomethine ylides, nitrile oxides

[†]In Commemoration of the 150th Birth Anniversary of Acharya Prafulla Chandra Ray.

Among the 1,3-dipolar species, the nitron chemistry¹⁻⁹ has been the most thoroughly investigated, frequently reviewed from the 1960s^{3,4} and is ultimately dominated by their use as 1,3-dipoles in cycloaddition reactions. Nitrones were first prepared by Beckmann in 1890^{10,11}; the nomenclature was coined by Pfeiffer¹¹ in 1916: nitrones = 'nitrogen ketones'. Nitrones can be prepared by means of different procedures^{6,9-13}, viz. condensation of *N*-monosubstituted hydroxylamines with carbonyl compounds, dehydrogenation of *N,N*-disubstituted hydroxylamines, selective *N*-alkylation of oximes, *N*-oxidation of secondary amines, reactions of aromatic nitroso compounds with active methylene compounds etc. We developed a microwave assisted synthesis^{14,15} of *C,N*-disubstituted aldonitrones from aldehydes and *N*-substituted hydroxylamines; by this procedure nitrones are obtained in excellent yields with considerably reduced reaction times, of the order of minutes. The most common 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition reaction of nitrones is the formation of isoxazolidine using alkene dipolarophiles. The generated isoxazolidine cycloadducts contain up to three new contiguous chiral centres. Four reaction pathways are possible leading to different cycloadducts (Scheme 2). Isoxazolidines are reasonably stable and they act as templates in the synthesis of various natural products^{6-9,16}.

these cycloadducts. Unmasking of 1,3-aminoalcohol moiety can be achieved via reductive cleavage (catalytic hydrogenation over Raney Ni, Pd, Pt, Rh, sodium in liquid ammonia or alcohol, Zn and acetic acid, LiAlH₄, electrolytic reduction). Ring opening reactions of the isoxazolidines may be carried out to generate useful intermediates during the synthesis of various Natural Products. The key intermediate in the Corey's synthesis of potent proteasome inhibitor salinosporamide A (used as an anticancer agent) has been recently obtained¹⁸ from (*S*)-methyl 2-hydroxymethylpyroglutamate through chemoselective O-protection, regio- and stereoselective *N*-methylnitron cycloadditions and quaternization-elimination reactions. Nitron cycloaddition has also been used to produce the core structure of the total synthesis of potent alkaloid toxin anatoxin¹⁹. A review on the earlier work on catalysis of 1,3-dipolar cycloadditions has been published²⁰.

The regio- and stereochemical preferences of the cycloaddition reactions depend on the nature of the dipole and the dipolarophile employed. These are greatly influenced by steric as well as electronic factors. Moreover, remarkable changes can be encountered in the reaction rates and selectivities of these reactions by addition of different catalysts. With this in mind, we were initially

Scheme 2. 1,3-Dipolar cycloaddition reactions of acyclic aldonitrones to substituted olefins.

Some isoxazolidines are known to possess antibacterial activity¹⁷. Isoxazolidines can be regarded as masked 1,3-difunctionalised compounds^{6-9,16}, hence complex nitrogen heterocycles can be constructed by manipulation of

interested to study the experimental aspects of the cycloaddition reactions of acyclic and cyclic nitrones leading to the generation of some stereochemically defined five-membered heterocycles. Subsequently, the results that

we obtained regarding regio- and stereochemical preferences and reactivity of such reactions resulted an upsurge of interest in us to study the utility of DFT based theoretical models for a better understanding of the bonding nature, mechanism and energy sequences of such reactions. In the present review, we have attempted to present a consolidated picture of the experimental aspects of these reactions and their theoretical analysis in terms of DFT based reactivity indices, interaction energy calculations and activation parameters of the transition states.

2. Cycloaddition reactions of acyclic nitrones to substituted olefins – experimental aspects

2.1. Cycloaddition reactions of acyclic nitrones to substituted olefins

C,N-Disubstituted nitrones are one of the well studied and thoroughly investigated class of acyclic aldonitrones with broad synthetic potential^{7,8,9,16}. The cycloaddition reactions of these nitrones to olefins have been represented in Scheme 2 – four reaction pathways are possible.

The nomenclature of *ortho*- and *meta*- for describing the regiochemical paths to, and hence the cycloadducts themselves, has been accepted in the last few years, particularly by those exploring the theoretical aspects of 1,3-dipolar cycloadditions. The reactions involving monosubstituted olefins ($R = R^2 = H$) proceed with high degree of regioselectivity and give rise to 5-substituted (i.e. *ortho*) isoxazolidines for both electron donating (e.g. $R^1 = OR^{21,22}$) and electron withdrawing groups (e.g. $R^1 = COOMe^{21}$, CN^{21}) attached to the olefin. The cycloaddition reaction of *C*-phenyl-*N*-methyl nitrone ($R^3 = Ph$, $R^4 = Me$) and ethyl vinyl ether ($R^1 = OEt$) gives rise to a 1 : 1 mixture of *cis* (PI) and *trans* (PII) 5-substituted isoxazolidines²².

Electronic as well as steric effects are important in determining product stereochemistry; a few instances are quoted below. The reaction of methyl acrylate ($R^1 = COOMe$) to *C,N*-diphenyl nitrone ($R^3 = R^4 = Ph$) gives rise to mixture of *cis* (PI, 57%) and *trans* (PII, 43%) 5-substituted isoxazolidines²¹. On the other hand, the reaction between *C*-phenyl-*N*-*t*-butyl nitrone ($R^3 = Ph$, $R^4 = t$ -butyl) and methyl acrylate ($R^1 = COOMe$) gives the *trans* 5-carbomethoxy isoxazolidine (PII, 91%, *ortho* adduct) as the major product²³. This is in marked contrast with the cycloaddition reaction behaviour of *C*-phenyl-*N*-

methyl nitrone ($R^3 = Ph$, $R^4 = Me$) which gives rise to the *cis* 5-carbomethoxy isoxazolidine (PI, 77%) as the dominant product. The cycloaddition reaction of *C,N*-diphenyl nitrone ($R^3 = R^4 = Ph$) to styrene ($R^1 = Ph$) produces a mixture of *cis* (PI, 90%) and *trans* (PII, 10%) 5-phenyl isoxazolidines²¹. The stereoselectivity decreases in the cycloaddition reaction of *C*-phenyl-*N*-methyl nitrone ($R^3 = Ph$, $R^4 = Me$) to styrene ($R^1 = Ph$), when the *cis* (PI) and *trans* (PII) adducts are generated in the ratio 67 : 33. The reactions of *C*-furfuryl-*N*-benzyl nitrone ($R^3 = furfuryl$, $R^4 = CH_2Ph$) to ethyl vinyl ether ($R^1 = OEt$) and α,β -unsaturated esters like ethyl acrylate ($R^1 = COOEt$) and methyl acrylate ($R^1 = COOMe$) give rise to *ortho* regioisomers as the major products²⁴. The 4 : 5 substitution ratio increases as the electron withdrawing ability of the functional group attached to the olefin increases. Very strong electron withdrawing groups (e.g. $R^1 = NO_2^{23,25}$, SO_2Ph^{26}) attached to the olefin give rise to 4-substituted (i.e. *meta*) regioisomers. Nitroethylene ($R^1 = NO_2^{23}$) readily reacts with *C*-phenyl-*N*-methyl nitrone ($R^3 = Ph$, $R^4 = Me$) to give a 2 : 1 mixture of *cis* (PIII) and *trans* (PIV) *meta* adducts. Electron donating groups on the nitrone increases the 4 : 5 substitution ratio. The cycloaddition reaction of electron donating *C*-cyclopropyl-*N*-methyl nitrone ($R^3 = cyclopropyl$, $R^4 = Me$) to electron deficient alkene acrylonitrile ($R^1 = CN$) gives rise to *meta* isoxazolidines as the major products²⁷. On the other hand, *ortho* adducts are obtained exclusively from the reaction of *C,N*-diphenyl nitrone ($R^3 = R^4 = Ph$) to acrylonitrile ($R^1 = CN$)²¹.

1,1-Disubstituted olefins show high regioselectivity and give *ortho*-pathway products²¹. Strong electron withdrawing groups give *meta*-pathway products, e.g. the cycloaddition reaction of *C,N*-diphenyl nitrone to diethyl methylene malonate ($R = R^1 = COOEt$, $R^2 = H$) was reported to give exclusively the 4,4-dicarbomethoxy isoxazolidine²⁸.

The cycloaddition reactions of nitrones to disubstituted olefins give rise to 2,3,4,5-tetrasubstituted isoxazolidines. In case of unsymmetrically 1,2-disubstituted olefins, it is expected that the regio- and stereoselectivity of the reaction course will be directed by both the substituents. Initially, little attention had been paid to the study of such reactions – this encouraged us to commence systematic investigations on these reactions several years ago. Other research groups also contributed, and at present there exists a large database on the

regio- and stereoselectivities of acyclic nitronc cycloadditions to disubstituted olefins. Mobinikhaledi *et al.*²⁹ has reported a series of cycloaddition reactions of *C*-aryl-*N*-phenyl nitrones to styrene, 4-chlorostyrene, ethyl crotonate, acrylonitrile and methyl acrylate. The *ortho* substituted isoxazolidines were obtained preferentially as the major isomer in each case except that in case of ethyl crotonate. The latter afforded *meta* adducts, with respect to the carboxy group (R¹; for disubstituted dipolarophiles, *ortho* and *meta* cycloaddition pathways are designated with respect to substituent R¹).

We have been engaged since long in studying the regio- and stereochemical course of the cycloaddition reactions of acyclic and cyclic nitrones. Some of our experimental findings regarding cycloadditions of acyclic nitrones are listed in Table 1. We studied in details the cycloaddition reactions of substituted cinnamic acid amides (R¹ = piperidinyloxo, R² = phenyl/*para* substituted phenyl) to *C,N*-diaryl nitrones³⁰⁻³² (Table 1). The cycloadditions of *C*-aryl-*N*-(4-chlorophenyl)nitrones³² to dipolarophiles had not been investigated earlier. The reactions were carried

out in refluxing toluene for periods extending to several hours. Total yields of cycloadducts varied from over 60% to over 90%. The effect of varying aryl substituents, both on the nitronc as well as the dipolarophile were investigated. The *para* substituents on the dipole and dipolarophile varied from strongly electron withdrawing nitro group to the electron donating methoxy groups along the series. The *C,N*-diaryl nitrones were found to react in the *trans*-form; a high degree of selectivity was observed – the *endo*-carbonyl mode of approach predominated. The cycloaddition reactions gave rise to 3,4-*trans*-4,5-*trans*-4-piperidinyloxoisoxazolidines (PIII) as the major products and 3,4-*cis*-4,5-*trans*-4-piperidinyloxoisoxazolidines (PIV) as the minor adducts. Small amounts of regioisomeric products 3,4-*trans*-4,5-*trans*-5-piperidinyloxoisoxazolidines (PI) were also generated in some reactions when the aryl groups had electron-withdrawing substituents. We further observed the generation of ring opened compounds of isoxazolidine rings in few cases³². These were derived from the major cycloadducts (PIII), and were identified from the presence of two hydroxyl

Table 1. Relative proportion of products obtained from cycloaddition reactions of *C,N*-disubstituted aldonitrones to electron deficient disubstituted dipolarophiles

Dipolarophile		Nitronc		Product ratios				Ref.
R ¹ /R	R ²	R ³	R ⁴	PI	PII	PIII	PIV	
R ¹ = Piperidinyloxo, R = H	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	4-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	Ph	8	0	82	10	30, 31
	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	Ph	9	0	81	10	
	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	Ph	Ph	0	0	91	9	
	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	4-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	8	0	76 ^a	11	32
	4-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	4-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	10	0	60	30 ^a	
	Ph	4-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	15	0	69	17	
	4-OMeC ₆ H ₄	4-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	6	0	85	9	
	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	3-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	7	0	81	12	
	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	Ph	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	5	0	88	7	
	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	4-OMeC ₆ H ₄	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	7	0	81	12	
R ¹ = NO ₂ , R = H	Ph	4-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	Ph	0	0	84	16	38
	Ph	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	Ph	0	0	82	18	
	Ph	Ph	Ph	0	0	86	14	
	Ph	4-OMeC ₆ H ₄	Ph	0	0	75	25	
	Ph	2-Furyl	Ph	0	0	71	29	
R ¹ = COPh, R = H	Ph	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	Ph	0	0	87	13	39
	4-OMeC ₆ H ₄	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	Ph	0	0	92	8	
	Ph	Ph	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	0	0	90	10	
	Ph	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	Me	14	0	78	8	
	Ph	4-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	Ph	9	0	81	10	39
	Ph	2-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	Ph	9	0	77	14	
	4-OMeC ₆ H ₄	4-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	Ph	5	0	85	10	

^aThe corresponding ring opened compound was obtained.

protons >N-OH and >5-OH which showed correlation to H-3, H-4 and H-5 in the TOCSY spectra.

The structures and substitution patterns of the three types of cycloadducts were settled with the aid of spectroscopical (particularly NMR) techniques and X-ray crystallographic analysis. Attention was also given to the conformational analysis and energy minimisation studies of the regio- and stereoisomers by use of computational methods³¹.

Our initial studies had involved cycloaddition reactions of *C*-aryl-*N*-phenyl nitrones to conjugated lactone butenolide³³ – which of course is a *cis*-disubstituted α,β -unsaturated carbalkoxy dipolarophile; at this stage only one paper had been published earlier on the cycloaddition of nitrones to unsaturated lactones. Two stereoisomeric 2-phenyl-3-aryl-2,3,6,6a-tetrahydrofuro[3,4-*d*]-isoxazol-4(3*aH*)-one cycloadducts and a ring-opened butanolide derivative were obtained in each case.

We then extended our studies to the cycloadditions of these nitrones to ethyl crotonate³⁴. These reactions occurred with high selectivity to furnish 3,4-*trans*-4,5-*trans*-2,3-diaryl-4-carbomethoxy-5-methylisoxazolidines as major cycloadducts; the 3,4-*cis*-4,5-*trans* stereoisomers were obtained as minor products. These reactions were completely regioselective – no regioisomeric cycloadducts PI or PII were formed. Earlier, preliminary reports^{21,35} on the cycloaddition reaction of methyl crotonate ($R^1 = \text{COOMe}$, $R^2 = \text{Me}$) to *C,N*-diphenyl nitron ($R^3 = R^4 = \text{Ph}$) showed that a mixture of 3,4-*cis*-4,5-*trans* (PIV, 15%) and 3,4-*trans*-4,5-*trans* (PIII, 85%)-4-carbomethoxy substituted isoxazolidines were formed.

Studies on the cycloadditions of acyclic nitrones to methyl cinnamate and aryl-substituted methyl cinnamate esters were found to follow similar trends to the cinnamic acid amides – the 3,4-*trans*-4,5-*trans*-5-aryl-4-carbomethoxy substituted cycloadducts (PIII) being obtained as the major products, with smaller amounts of their 3,4-*cis*-4,5-*trans* (PIV) stereoisomers³⁶.

Introduction of a second carbalkoxy group in the dipolarophiles caused a dramatic increase in reaction rate, and selectivity to furnish single cycloadducts in the reactions of *C,N*-diarylnitrones with benzylidene malonates³⁷. The reactions occurred with very high selectivity and to furnish 3,5-*trans*-2,3,5-triaryl-4,4-dicarbomethoxy isoxazolidines (PIV; $R = R^1 = \text{COOEt}$, $R^2 = \text{Ph}$) exclusively in nearly quantitative yields. This is in contrast with the nitron cycloadditions to other α,β -conjugated

carbonyl derivatives where two diastereoisomeric (and on occasion regioisomeric) cycloadducts were generally obtained. Further to be noted is that the cycloadducts were obtained from the *endo*-aryl approach to the nitron, in contrast to the *endo*-carbonyl, *exo*-aryl approach for the cinnamic acid derivatives to furnish the major 3,4-*trans*-4,5-*trans*-5-aryl-4-carbalkoxy/carboxamido adduct (PIII).

When we carried out the cycloaddition reactions of β -nitrostyrene³⁸ ($R^1 = \text{NO}_2$, $R^2 = \text{Ph}$) to *C,N*-diaryl nitrones, we obtained a diastereomeric mixture of isoxazolidines by the *meta* pathway: 3,4-*trans*-4,5-*trans*-4-nitro (PIII) adducts were generated selectively as the major products from each reaction (Table 1).

We have recently reported the reactions of *C,N*-disubstituted aldonitrones to chalcones^{39,40}. 3,4-*trans*-4,5-*trans*-4-carbonyl adduct (PIII, *meta*-isomer) was obtained as the major adduct in each case. During the course of study, we also observed that the product composition depends on the nature of the nitrogen as well as the *C*-aryl substituents of the reacting nitron for these reactions (Table 1). The cycloaddition reaction of *C*-(4-chlorophenyl)-*N*-phenyl nitron to benzylidene acetophenone gave rise to two diastereomers PIII and PIV^{39,40}. However, three products were generated from the reactions of *C*-(4-chlorophenyl)-*N*-methyl nitron^{39,40} and *C*-(4-nitrophenyl)-*N*-phenyl nitron^{39,40} with the same dipolarophile. These experimental findings were rationalised in terms of DFT studies which have been dealt with in the final section of this review.

We ascertained the structures and stereochemistry of the generated cycloadducts in each of our investigations by NMR (with extensive use of two-dimensional NMR spectroscopy) and X-Ray crystallographic studies. The ORTEP views of a few selected cycloadducts from our work are shown in Scheme 3^{32,37-39}.

The reaction rates and the selectivities of nitron cycloadditions have attracted researchers all over the world and extensive studies are still reported to improve the reaction conditions. Anabha *et al.*⁴¹ have recently reported 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition reactions of nitrones to benzoquinones resulting in the formation of benzisoxazolidines. Ramamoorthy *et al.*⁴² demonstrated the inclusion of α -phenyl-*N-p*-methylphenyl nitron in β -cyclodextrin and reported the remarkably fast cycloaddition reaction of the complex with olefins in the solid state. According to a recent report⁴³, the cycloadditions between *C,N*-disubstituted aldonitrones and *N*-vinylamides can be conve-

	R	R ¹	R ²	R ³	R ⁴
I (PIII)	COOEt	COOEt	Ph	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	Ph
II (PIII)	H	Piperidinyloxo	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	4-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	4-ClC ₆ H ₄
III (PIII)	H	NO ₂	Ph	4-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	4-ClC ₆ H ₄
IV (PIII)	H	NO ₂	Ph	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	Me
V (PIII)	H	COPh	Ph	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	Ph
VI (PIII)	H	COPh	4-OMeC ₆ H ₄	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	Ph
VII (PIII)	H	COPh	Ph	4-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	Ph
VIII (PIII)	H	COPh	Ph	2-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	Ph
IX (PI)	H	Piperidinyloxo	4-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	Ph

Scheme 3. Structures of some cycloadducts (ORTEP views) from the reactions of *C,N*-disubstituted aldonitrone and electron deficient dipolarophiles.

niently achieved by an improved procedure under solvent free conditions in a very short reaction time with little or no formation of the degradation products. The reactions were performed in refluxing solution and also under solvent free conditions with 1 : 1 molar ratios of the enamide and the nitrone. The reactions leading to good yields of the expected cycloadducts were remarkably accelerated (~200 times) under solvent free conditions.

Cycloaddition reactions of *C,N*-disubstituted aldonic nitrones with benzannulated cyclooctyne (strained cycloalkynes) have been reported recently⁴⁴. Recently⁴⁵, it has been reported that α -amino acid derived nitrones like *N*-benzyl aspartate nitrone and its dithiolone protected form exist exclusively as (*E*)-isomers at room temperature in CDCl_3 solution and the cycloaddition reactions of the protected form to alkenes provide better results than those of the nitrones themselves.

1,3-Dipolar cycloaddition reactions of various acyclic nitrones to 5-methylhydantoin derivatives have been reported recently⁴⁶. The reactions gave rise to new chiral spiroadducts in good yields through a regio- and stereospecific pathway. It has also been reported⁴⁷ that the monomode microwave assisted regio- and stereoselective cycloaddition reactions of *C*-(3-indolyl)-*N*-phenyl nitrone to a number of olefinic dipolarophiles give rise to isoxazolidines in high yields, which are conformationally constrained mimetics of indole-3-propionic acid of biological significance. 1,3-Dipolar cycloaddition reactions of substituted vinylphosphonate with nitrile oxide and nitrones have also been reported⁴⁸.

2.2. Cycloaddition reactions of cyclic nitrones to substituted olefins

The cycloaddition reactions of cyclic nitrones to substituted olefins have been represented in Scheme 4. A number of communications have reported the cycloaddition reactions of cyclic nitrones^{7,9,49}.

An interesting early application of the cycloaddition of cyclic nitrone was to synthesize fire-ant venom solenopsin A⁵⁰. The diastereoselective synthesis of pyrazolyl isoxazolidines has been reported⁵¹ recently via 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition reactions of substituted pyrazolyl nitrones to β -nitro styrene and ethyl-vinyl ether. Pyrazole derivatives are known to exhibit wide range of biological properties and anticoagulant activity. The reaction involving α -nitro styrene afforded the *endo* diastereoisomer exclusively. On the other hand, the *exo* diastereoisomer was the major cycloadduct (*de* > 95%) generated from

the cycloaddition reactions of substituted pyrazolyl nitrones to ethyl vinyl ether.

1,3-Dipolar cycloadditions of several cyclic nitrones have been studied by us. The cyclic nitrones investigated were Δ^1 -dehydro-pyrroline-1-oxide (1-pyrroline-1-oxide), 3,4,5,6-tetrahydro-pyridine-1-oxide and Δ^3 -dehydro-morpholine-4-oxide. These cycloadditions were carried out to *N*-cinnamoylpiperidine and derivatives⁵²⁻⁵⁵. Interesting results were obtained for the three nitrones, which showed different reactivity profiles. The reactions of 1-pyrroline-1-oxide to 1-cinnamoyl piperidine ($R^1 = \text{piperidinyloxo}$, $R^2 = \text{Ph}$) and its derivatives gave a regioisomeric mixture of 2,3-*trans*-3,3*a*-*cis*-2-piperidinyloxo (PV, $n = 1$) and 2,3-*trans*-3,3*a*-*cis*-3-piperidinyloxo isoxazolidines (PVII, $n = 1$)^{52,53}, both regioisomers being formed by preferential *endo*-mode of attack.

However, when we reacted corresponding 6-membered nitrone ($n = 2$), viz. 3,4,5,6-tetrahydropyridine-1-oxide ($n = 2$) to substituted cinnamic acid piperidides ($R^1 = \text{oxopiperidinyloxo}$, $R^2 = \text{aryl}$) all four types of cycloadducts PV, PVI, PVII and PVIII were obtained from the reaction mixture^{52,54}. Cycloadducts PVII (XII) were the major products. These cycloadducts showed extreme conformational mobility in solution at room temperature – two different flippomers arising due to flipping of the isoxazolidine ring by inversion of the ring-juncture nitrogen were present in deuteriochloroform solution at ambient temperature (Scheme 5) – this was detected by NMR analysis. X-Ray crystallographic analysis also showed the presence of both flippomers in the solid state⁵⁴.

A series of unexpected cycloadducts [XII; $R^1 = \text{Ph}$, 4- ClC_6H_4 , 4- MeOC_6H_4 , 4- $\text{O}_2\text{NC}_6\text{H}_4$; $R^2 = (\text{morpholin-4-yl})\text{oxy}$] along with normal cycloadducts (XIV), corresponding to PVI have been isolated from the 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition of 3,4-dehydromorpholine *N*-oxide to *N*-cinnamoylamides and analysed by NMR-TOCSY spectral analysis, and then X-ray crystallographic analysis to reveal novel structures (Scheme 6). A plausible iminium-oxonium ion mechanism was proposed involving the initially formed 1 : 1 cycloadducts. This communication breaks new ground in 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition – the ring oxygen plays a key role; such products are not formed from cycloadditions of the cyclic nitrones 3,4,5,6-tetrahydro-pyridine-1-oxide or 1-pyrroline-1-oxide or their substituted derivatives.

Ali *et al.*⁵⁶ recently reported an extension of our work by investigating the reactions of the more hindered and

Scheme 4. 1,3-Dipolar cycloaddition reactions of cyclic nitrones to substituted olefins.

Scheme 5. Flippomers of PVII; $n = 2$, $R^1 = \text{CO piperidinyl}$, $R^2 = \text{phenyl}$.

XIII : $R^1 = \text{aryl}$, $R^2 = (\text{morpholin-4-yl})\text{oxy}$
XIV : $R = \text{aryl}$, $R^2 = \text{H}$

Scheme 6. Unexpected products from the cycloaddition of 3,4-dehydromorpholine *N*-oxide to *N*-cinnamoylamides.

chiral 4-butyloxycarbonyl-3,4,5,6-tetrahydropyridin-1-oxide to several dipolarophiles. He reported the formation of a mixture of cycloadducts, and commented on the stereo- and face selectivity of these cycloadditions.

We have recently reported⁵⁷ the cycloaddition reactions of 1-pyrroline-1-oxide to benzylidene acetophenone

and methyl cinnamate. Both the reactions afforded a diastereomeric mixture of *meta* adducts. We observed that the reaction involving α,β -unsaturated ketone was *exo* selective. On the other hand, the *endo* isomer was obtained predominantly from the reaction involving α,β -unsaturated ester. We then rationalized the experimental findings in terms of DFT based reactivity indices and the activation energies of the located transition states. The regio- and stereochemistry of cycloadducts in each study was determined from two-dimensional NMR and X-ray studies. ORTEP view and packing of the cycloadduct obtained from benzylidene acetone has been shown in Scheme 7.

2.3. Effect of Lewis acid catalysts on the cycloaddition reactions

Since leading researcher Kobayashi's 1991 paper⁵⁸ on their catalytic effect in water, the range of research applications for lanthanide triflate catalysts has exploded – high conversions can be achieved by using small quantities of lanthanide triflate catalysts. The principal properties of lanthanide triflates as Lewis acid catalysts have been reported recently⁵⁹. It was natural that application of such catalysts will be studied in 1,3-dipolar cycloadditions, in addition to other weak Lewis acids. Hence, catalytic studies of cycloaddition reactions have gained wide importance in recent years⁶⁰⁻⁶⁴; the regio- and stereoselectivities have been reported to be affected significantly by the addition of Lewis acid catalyst. Several

(i) ORTEP view of the asymmetric unit content (hydrogen's are drawn as spheres with arbitrary radius) The ellipsoids encompass 50% of the electron density of the atom [A and B] of cycloadduct PVII⁵⁷

(ii) A single molecule (A) viewed along the N2-C3 bond showing the puckering of the two fused five-membered rings The size of ellipsoids is reduced (30% of the electron density) and hydrogen's omitted for clarity

(iii) Packing in the crystal

Scheme 7. X-Ray crystallographic analysis of cycloadduct PVII obtained from the reaction of 1-pyrroline-1-oxide and benzylidene acetophenone⁵⁷

initial reports were published in which significant enhancement of rates and selectivities were reported in nitrono cycloadditions catalysed by lanthanide triflates as well as other weak Lewis acids to very simple dipolarophiles possessing a carbonyl group conjugated to the double bond, which were not particularly hindered sterically^{62,64}. Gothelf²⁰ had explained that the strategy of the catalytic enhancement is to alter the relative ener-

gies of the frontier molecular orbitals (FMOs) of one of the substrates, the dipole or the dipolarophile, by preferentially coordinating the substrate to the Lewis acid catalyst. Being a strong electron acceptor, a Lewis acid catalyst can decrease the energy of the FMO_{alkene} via coordination of enone to the Lewis acid catalyst. Consequently, acceleration of the reaction can be achieved due to decreased energy gap between the interacting FMOs for the

normal electron demand reactions. The dipole can coordinate to the Lewis acid catalyst in reactions involving electron rich alkenes resulting in the decrease of the LUMO_{dipole} energy. Thus, an enhanced reaction rate can be achieved in these reactions by dipole-Lewis acid coordination for *inverse electron demand reactions*. Shimizu *et al.*⁶³ reported that 1,3-dipoles react with Lewis acid catalysts to give unstable ionic salts that exhibit 1,3-dipolar nature and undergo highly stereoselective cycloaddition reactions with the dipolarophiles.

We recently studied⁶⁵ the effect of mild Lewis acid catalysts on 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition reactions of *C,N*-disubstituted aldonitrone to α,β -unsaturated ketones. The steric bulk of the reactants, as well as the electronic demands on the dipolarophile double bond were considerably different from the simple systems studied by the pioneering investigators. Our experimental data for the reaction between *C*-(4-chlorophenyl)-*N*-phenyl nitrone and benzylidene acetophenone are listed in Table 2. The uncatalysed reaction gave rise to two diastereomeric cycloadducts (entry 1) by the *meta* pathway with the ma-

Table 2. Experimental results for cycloaddition reactions of *C*-(4-chlorophenyl)-*N*-phenyl nitrone to benzylidene acetophenone in presence of mild Lewis acid catalysts

Entry	Additive ^a	Run time ^b	Total conversion ^c (%)	Product ratios	
				PIII	PIV
1	-	20	69	87	13
2	Li(OTf)	3	93	86	14
3	MgBr ₂ .Et ₂ O	3	78	65	35
4	Zn(OTf) ₂	7	42	67	33
5	Cu(OTf) ₂	28	-	Not detected	
6	Yb(OTf) ₃	28	-	Not detected	

^aThe additives (Lewis acid catalysts) were taken in 0.2 molar proportion of the nitrone in each cycloaddition.

^bThe cycloadditions were performed in toluene at 110°C under nitrogen atmosphere and monitored after regular time intervals by 300 MHz ¹H NMR spectroscopy.

for *endo* product. The reactions were monitored by 300 MHz ¹H NMR spectroscopy at regular time intervals. The total conversions and product ratios were evaluated from the integrated intensities of the isoxazolidine ring protons of the cycloadducts in 300 MHz ¹H NMR spectra of the crude reaction mixtures. The total conversion was 69% with the diastereomeric excess 74% after 20 h. There was a remarkable reduction in the reaction time in presence of lithium triflate with almost unaltered diastereomeric

excess compared to the uncatalyzed cycloaddition reaction. Magnesium bromide and zinc triflate also resulted in reduction of the reaction time. Both the catalysts led to considerably reduced diastereoselectivity. This was apparently due to the greater bulk of the complexed unsaturated ketonic species, which would inhibit the *endo*-approach. However, no products were detected in 300 MHz ¹H NMR spectra of the crude reaction mixtures for ytterbium triflate and copper triflate catalyzed reactions even after several hours. This was in stark contrast to the positive catalytic enhancements for ytterbium triflate and copper triflate reported earlier for simpler systems⁶². There are two explanations – (i) the complexed dipolarophile becomes very bulky preventing approach of the nitrone; (ii) the nitrone-Lewis acid complexation occurs preferentially in view of the difficulty of formation of the sterically congested dipolarophile complex, thereby blocking the cycloaddition pathway.

Bortolini *et al.*⁶⁶ reported cycloaddition reactions of *C*-phenyl-*N*-benzyl nitrone and *C*-phenyl-*N*-methyl nitrone to vinyl ethers catalyzed by Er(OTf)₃ in bmim(OTf) [1-butyl-3-methyl imidazolium, TfO⁻ = CF₃SO₃⁻] at 25°C under different experimental conditions. For a molar ratio *C*-phenyl-*N*-benzyl nitrone/*n*-butyl vinyl ether/Er(OTf)₃ of 1 : 20 : 0.2, nearly complete conversion was reported in 3 h at 25°C. The reaction was much faster and selective in presence of ionic liquids compared to that under conventional conditions. NMR studies have indicated that Eu(fod)₃ can selectively activate (*Z*)-configuration of *C*-carbomethoxy-*N*-benzyl nitrone in the (*E*), (*Z*)-equilibrium mixtures of nitrones⁶⁷. The cycloadditions of the nitrone with vinyl esters was reported to give rise to the *trans* cycloadduct in a highly stereoselective manner in presence of Eu(fod)₃. Uncatalysed cycloadditions of nitrones with vinyl esters yield a mixture of *cis* and *trans* cycloadducts.

3. Mechanism of 1,3-dipolar cycloadditions

Huisgen^{2,68,69} and coworkers proposed a single step, four center, six electron, *supra-supra* concerted mechanism [$\pi 4_s + \pi 4_s$] for 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition reactions (Scheme 8). This was in accordance with the Woodward-Hoffmann concepts⁷⁰ in which the two new bonds are both partially formed in the transition state, although not necessarily to the same extent. This was criticized by Firestone⁷¹ proposing a stepwise mechanism involving biradical intermediate. Huisgen^{69,72} duly replied to Firestone's arguments in a following communication and

Scheme 8. Huisgen's and Firestone's proposed mechanisms

also mentioned⁷² the most convincing exceptions to the concerted path. However, these mechanistic exceptions could well be confined to the realm of stepwise mechanism via dipolar intermediate and not to that of stepwise mechanism via diradical intermediate as proposed by Firestone.

Numerous experimental and theoretical studies have concluded that the four-centre concerted pathway explains the reactivities and selectivities of a wide range of 1,3-dipolar cycloadditions. The diradical pathway is not found to be acceptable by an overwhelming majority of researchers working on both experimental and theoretical aspects of 1,3-dipolar cycloadditions.

3.1. Theoretical approaches

Application of Perturbation theory has proved to be a valuable tool to generalize diverse organic phenomena. Herndon⁷³ has reviewed the application of perturbation theory to cycloaddition reactions. Scheme 9 shows the orbital interactions of two molecules involved in a cy-

Scheme 9. Orbital interaction of two molecules involved in a cycloaddition reaction.

cloaddition reaction. Interaction of two molecules involved in a cycloaddition is accompanied by energy changes. A

quantitative second order perturbation expression was derived by Salem⁷⁴ regarding these energy transformations.

In the earlier approaches, the contribution of coulombic repulsion (or dipole-dipole repulsion) was neglected in comparison to the frontier orbital interaction unless the reactants are charged or particularly polar. Interaction between only the frontier orbitals of both reactants was considered⁷⁵, since the inverse dependence of the stabilization energy on orbital energy difference ensured that interaction energy terms involving the frontier orbitals will be larger than the others. Thus, the perturbation equation was simplified to the following form, where only the interaction energy term of the frontier orbitals of HOMO and LUMO were considered :

$$\Delta E_{\text{covalent}} = 2(C_d^{\text{HO}} C_a^{\text{LU}} \Delta \beta_{ad} + C_d^{\text{HO}} C_a^{\text{LU}} \Delta \beta_{a'd'})^2 / (E_D^{\text{HO}} - E_A^{\text{LU}}) + 2(C_d^{\text{LU}} C_a^{\text{HO}} \Delta \beta_{ad} + C_d^{\text{LU}} C_a^{\text{HO}} \Delta \beta_{a'd'})^2 / (E_A^{\text{HO}} - E_D^{\text{LU}})$$

Fukui⁷⁵ also argued that the frontier orbital interactions should be even more important than is implied by the inverse dependence of the stabilization energy on orbital energy differences since, during the course of reaction, the difference between the energies of the frontier orbitals of the two reactants will diminish. This was called "the principle of narrowing of inter-frontier level separation"⁷⁵.

Sustmann and Trill⁷⁶ classified 1,3-dipolar cycloadditions into three types with respect to the 1,3-dipolar species (HOMO controlled, HOMO-LUMO controlled and LUMO controlled) depending on the relative disposition of the frontier orbitals, leading to further simplification. Formation of the regioisomer is predicted for which the HOMO-LUMO coefficient pairings are [large-large + small-small]. It is apparent that greater is the differentiation in the magnitude of the FMO coefficients in each of the reactants, the greater would be the regioselectivity.

Houk and coworkers^{77,78} demonstrated a set of generalized frontier orbitals of 1,3-dipoles and dipolarophiles and their relative reactivities by CNDO/2, INDO or the extended Hückel (EH) methods. The energy diagrams⁷⁸ (on the basis of CNDO/2 frontier orbital energy calculations) provided a consistent generalization of the relative reactivities of 1,3-dipoles. These theoretical analyses dealt with the simple systems. Houk's papers represented an enormous step forward in explaining reactivities and regioselectivities of 1,3-dipolar cycloadditions which had till then baffled researchers in this field.

3.2. DFT based reactivity indices

The selectivities of 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition reactions of nitrones have been recently analyzed in terms of DFT based reactivity indices by a number of leading research groups. The regioselectivities of a number of types of nitron cycloaddition, such as those between C-(methoxycarbonyl)-*N*-methyl nitrones and methyl acrylate/vinyl acetate^{79,80}, *C,N*-diphenyl nitron and acrolein⁸¹/maleimide⁸², *C*-(hetaryl) nitrones and methyl acrylate/vinyl acetate⁸³ have been reported to be in conformity with those predicted by the relative electrophilicity patterns. This approach has been found to be more reliable than the frontier molecular orbital theory⁸⁴. Chattaraj *et al.*^{85,86} have recently reviewed the utility of the concept of electrophilicity index and its various extensions.

The basic theoretical concepts which have been applied in our analysis of 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition reactions are well-established; hence these have not been dealt with in details, only the equations have been given, and relevant papers cited. Moreover, in a recent paper, Chattaraj has dealt with these concepts in some details⁸⁷.

Electronegativity (χ) is defined as the negative of chemical potential⁸⁸. The electronic chemical potential⁸⁹ μ is the index pointing to the direction of the electronic flux during the cycloaddition, i.e. the charge transfer (CT) within the system in its ground state. Parr *et al.*⁹⁰ introduced the concept of absolute hardness. Hardness⁹⁰ η specifies the resistance to the charge transfer process. μ and η can be expressed in terms of ionization potential (I) and electron affinity (A)^{87,91} as : $\mu = -(I + A)/2$ and $\eta = I - A$.

Softness⁸⁵ S is the reciprocal of hardness and is given by $S = 1/\eta$. In some⁷⁹ communications, global softness is given by $S = 1/2\eta$; the value of 2 is arbitrary, to create a symmetry between $(I - A)/2$ and $(I + A)/2$ ^{90,91}.

μ and η can be rewritten by very simple operational formulation in terms of the one-electron orbital energies of FMO, viz. the HOMO and LUMO using Koopman's theorem⁹²,

$$\mu \approx (\epsilon_{\text{HOMO}} + \epsilon_{\text{LUMO}})/2$$

$$\eta \approx \epsilon_{\text{LUMO}} - \epsilon_{\text{HOMO}}$$

Parr *et al.*⁹¹ defined the global electrophilicity index ω by :

$$\omega = \mu^2/2\eta$$

The global electrophilicity index^{84,85,93,94} ω measures the

stabilization in energy when the system acquires an additional electronic charge from the environment.

The Fukui functions⁹⁵ of an atom in a molecule have proved to be useful criteria to characterise the reactive sites within a chemical species. The Fukui functions f_k^+ (for nucleophilic attack) and f_k^- (for electrophilic attack) at the k -th atom is given by the following expressions :

$$f_k^+ = q_k(N + 1) - q_k(N)$$

$$f_k^- = q_k(N) - q_k(N - 1)$$

where $q_k(N + 1)$, $q_k(N)$, $q_k(N - 1)$ represent the respective electron populations of the cationic, neutral and anionic systems on the k -th atom.

The local electrophilicity index^{87,96-98} ω_k^+ is expressed as $\omega_k^+ = \omega f_k^+$.

The preferred interaction between the reactants will take place through the most electrophilic site of the electrophile and the most nucleophilic site of the nucleophile.

The condensed local softnesses s_k^+ and s_k^- are calculated as the product of condensed Fukui functions f_k^+ and f_k^- and the global softness S

$$s_k^+ = S f_k^+ ; s_k^- = S f_k^-$$

Regioselectivity for four centre reactions can be analyzed in terms of softness matching index⁹⁹⁻¹⁰¹ Δ_{ij}^{kl} defined in terms of local softnesses by : $\Delta_{ij}^{kl} = (s_i^- - s_k^+)^2 + (s_j^- - s_l^+)^2$; where atoms i and j of the nucleophile interact with atoms k and l of the electrophile respectively to give rise to the preferred regioisomer. The concept is based on simultaneous fulfillment of the local HSAB principle at both the termini according to Gazquez-Méndez rule. Gazquez-Méndez rule¹⁰²⁻¹⁰⁶ states "the interaction between two chemical species is favored when it takes place through the atoms with approximately equal softnesses". Geerlings and coworkers¹⁰⁶ had applied the criterion to rationalize the regioselectivities of normal electron demand Diels-Alder reactions. The reaction pathway involving lower value of softness matching index Δ_{ij}^{kl} will be the favored one.

3.3. Computational work on nitron cycloadditions

In this Section of the present review, we have attempted to present our theoretical analysis of nitron cycloadditions in terms of DFT based reactivity indices, interaction energy calculations and activation parameters of the transition states. All our calculations were carried out on a personal computer using Gaussian 2003 set of programs along with the graphical interface Gauss View 2003¹⁰⁷.

Several *C*-aryl-*N*-methylnitrones and *C,N*-diarylnitrones were synthesised during the course of our work on 1,3-dipolar cycloadditions. Detailed systematic spectroscopic investigations of all these nitrones were undertaken^{15,108}. Our initial communications¹⁰⁸⁻¹¹⁰, as well as a more recent one¹¹¹, have dealt with computations of the optimised geometries and frontier orbital energies, as well as computations of their fundamental vibrational modes and ¹H- and ¹³C-NMR chemical shifts. Excellent agreement between the computed and experimental values were obtained.

We have recently reported^{39,57,111,112} the regioselectivities predicted by DFT based reactivity indices for the cycloaddition reactions of acyclic and cyclic nitrones to different disubstituted olefins. DFT/B3LYP/6-31G(d) calculated global and local properties for *C,N*-diphenyl nitron (N1), *C*-(4-chlorophenyl)-*N*-phenyl nitron (N2), *C*-(4-chlorophenyl)-*N*-methyl nitron (N3), 1-pyrroline-1-oxide (N4), benzylidene acetophenone (D1) and methyl crotonate (D2) have been listed in Table 3. The local properties have been calculated from the natural popula-

tron demand character of the cycloaddition reactions. This is also in conformity with the FMO energy predictions.

For the dipoles, the oxygen atom has greater condensed Fukui function f_k^- than the carbon atom. The local electrophilicity index ω_k^+ of C_β is higher than that of C_α in D1. Therefore the preferred two center interaction will take place between the oxygen atom of the dipoles and C_β of the dipolarophile D1. This is predicted to lead preferably to the generation of *meta* isoxazolindines; this is in complete agreement with our experimental findings.

Chandra and Nguyen¹¹³ pointed out that the evaluation of condensed Fukui functions requires atomic electron population in a molecule, which is not an unambiguously defined quantity. They further reported that electrostatic potential driven atomic charges^{114,115} and natural orbital based charges¹¹⁶ are more consistent for the calculation of Fukui functions. We have therefore recently reported¹¹² the condensed Fukui functions at the reactive sites of N1 and D2 on the basis of NPA¹¹⁶, MK¹¹⁴ and Chelp¹¹⁵ analyses and predicted the correct regioselectivities as shown in Scheme 11.

Table 3. DFT/B3LYP/6-31G(d) calculated global and local properties of nitrones and dipolarophiles, k being the atom site in the molecule

	HO (eV)	LU (eV)	μ (au)	η (au)	S (au)	ω (au)	k	f_k^+	f_k^-	ω_k^+ (eV)	s_k^+ (au)	s_k^- (au)
N1	-5.469	-1.769	-0.133	0.136	3.676	0.0650	O1	0.096	0.224	0.170	0.353	0.823
							C3	0.134	0.130	0.237	0.493	0.478
N2	-5.632	-1.850	-0.138	0.139	3.597	0.0685	O1	0.099	0.217	0.185	0.356	0.781
							C3	0.123	0.125	0.229	0.442	0.450
N3	-5.660	-1.524	-0.132	0.152	3.289	0.0573	O1	0.126	0.258	0.197	0.414	0.849
							C3	0.118	0.134	0.184	0.388	0.441
N4	-5.637	-0.169	-0.107	0.201	2.488	0.0285	O1	0.205	0.410	0.158	0.510	1.020
							C3	0.317	0.326	0.244	0.789	0.811
D1	-6.352	-1.962	-0.153	0.161	3.106	0.0727	C_α	0.036	0.089	0.071	0.112	0.276
							C_β	0.119	0.050	0.235	0.370	0.155
D2	-7.211	-0.980	-0.151	0.229	2.183	0.0498	C_α	0.099	0.300	0.216	0.655	0.134
							C_β	0.250	0.218	0.546	0.476	0.339

tion analysis (NPA). The predicted two-centre interactions for the cycloaddition reactions are shown in Scheme 10. The electronic chemical potentials μ of N1, N2, N3 and N4 are higher than that of D1. These indicate that the net charge transfer (CT) at these reactions will take place from the dipoles to the dipolarophile D1 along the cycloaddition process and therefore predicts the normal elec-

3.4. Formulation of interaction energy between the reacting species

The interactions between the electrophilic and nucleophilic centers of the reactants can be considered to predict the regioselectivity of cycloaddition reactions. Méndez *et al.*¹¹⁷ employed a perturbative orbital independent model to analyze the regioselectivity of the cycloaddition reac-

Scheme 10. Prediction of the favored interactions using DFT-based indices.

Scheme 11. Prediction of the favored interactions between N1 and D2.

tion of benzonitrile oxide to vinyl *p*-nitrobenzoate. The ionization potential and electron affinity of the reacting species are computed and the interaction energy between the reactants is considered in two steps happening in succession. One resulting from the chemical potential equalization principle¹¹⁸ and the other being the manifestation of the maximum hardness principle, i.e. the reshuffling step^{117,119,120}. Then, the regioselectivity for the cycloaddition reaction can be predicted by invoking the local viewpoint for the dipole and global viewpoint for the dipolarophile and vice versa.

We have recently applied¹¹² this model to predict the regioselectivity of the cycloaddition reaction between *C,N*-diphenyl nitron **N1** and methyl crotonate **D2** using NPA, MK and Chelp analyses.

3.5. Mechanism of 1,3-dipolar cycloadditions and activation parameters of the transition states

The controversy regarding concerted pericyclic mechanism and stepwise mechanism, as proposed by Huisgen and Firestone respectively have been addressed in a previous section in this communication. Subsequently, nu-

merous experimental and theoretical studies have concluded that the four-centre concerted pathway is very promising to explain the reactivities and selectivities of a wide range of 1,3-dipolar cycloadditions. Several *ab initio* MO calculations¹²¹⁻¹²⁵ have been carried out till date to comment on the mechanism of 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition reactions.

At present, the methods based on the Density Functional theory have emerged as alternative to traditional *ab initio* methods in terms of accuracy.

Highly sophisticated computations such as DFT/B3LYP studies have drawn the picture of a concerted mechanism. DFT/B3LYP/6-31G(d) and post HF calculations have been carried out to address the competition between concerted and stepwise diradical mechanisms in 1,3-dipolar cycloadditions¹²⁶. DFT/B3LYP/6-31G(d) study of parent nitron to ethene, cyclobutadiene and benzocyclobutadiene indicated that the reaction of cyclobutadiene and parent nitron represents a borderline case whereas alkene and benzocyclobutadiene facilitates the concerted cycloaddition pathway¹²⁶. Houk and coworkers¹²⁷ have

reported the performance of DFT, MP2 and CBS-QB3 methods for the prediction of activation barriers and reaction energetics of 1,3-dipolar cycloadditions and revised activation enthalpies for a standard set of hydrocarbon pericyclic reactions. The B3LYP/6-31G(d) method and basis set performs best for reaction enthalpies with a mean absolute deviation value of 2.4 kcal mol⁻¹, while the MPW1K method shows large errors for reaction energetics. The MP2 method gives the expected underestimation of barriers. Concerted and nearly synchronous transition states were predicted by all DFT and MP2 methods. DFT study of low lying stepwise paths for 1,3-dipolar cycloadditions of ethylene to diazomethane, nitrile oxide and nitrones have been reported¹²⁸ at DFT/B3LYP/6-31G(d), DFT/B3LYP/6-311++G(d,p) and QCISD/6-31G(d) level of theory; while the neutral cycloaddition partners preferred a concerted path, the charged partners strongly favored a stepwise path. The authors explained that the mechanistic crossover was induced by the polar influence of the charged species. DFT/B3LYP/6-31G(d) calculations have been reported¹²⁹ for 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition reactions of a chiral nitronone derived from L-erythrulose to methyl propiolate and acrylonitrile. The geometrical parameters of the transition states indicated a concerted mechanism for the cycloaddition reactions with asynchronous transition states. Structures and energetics of reactants, transition states and cycloadducts of cycloaddition reactions of *C,N*-diphenyl nitronone to fluorinated dipolarophiles of the ethylenic type and acetylenic types have been reported¹³⁰ at DFT/B3LYP/6-31G(d) level of theory. Analysis of the results on the different reaction pathways indicated a more or less synchronous mechanism.

1,3-Dipolar cycloaddition reactions of nitronone to mono-substituted alkenes have been the subject of a number of theoretical studies. Mention may be made of cycloadditions of *C*-(hetaryl)-*N*-methyl nitronones⁷⁹ to methyl acrylate and vinyl acetate analyzed in terms of DFT based reactivity indices and activation energy calculations, cycloadditions of *C,N*-diaryl nitronones to 2-nitropropene¹³¹, cycloadditions of diethoxyphosphoryl-*N*-methyl nitronone to allyl alcohol and methyl acrylate¹³² at DFT/B3LYP/6-31G(d,p) level of theory in terms of FMO analysis, DFT based reactivity indices and potential energy surface analysis. Combined experimental and theoretical study [at DFT/B3LYP/6-31G(d) level of theory] for 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition

of D-glyceraldehyde nitronones to alkyl acrylates and Oppolzer's sultam acrylamide have also been reported¹³³. Domingo¹³⁴ reported the theoretical study of the inverse electron demand dipolar cycloaddition reactions of nitronones with vinyl ethers at DFT/B3LYP/6-31G(d) level of theory. Magnuson and Pranata reported¹³⁵ a theoretical analysis for 1,3-dipolar cycloadditions of nitronone and fulminic acid to substituted ethylenes.

We were interested in extending the theoretical analysis of 1,3-dipoles to disubstituted alkene dipolarophiles, particularly to the systems of experimental interest to us. We have recently reported^{39,111} the activation energy calculations of the located transition states for the cycloadditions for *C,N*-disubstituted aldonitronones to α,β -unsaturated ketone and ester. Four possible reaction pathways for the *endo* and *exo* mode of approach along the *ortho* and *meta* channels were considered for each reaction. The DFT/B3LYP/6-31G(d) optimized transition states for the reaction between *C,N*-diphenyl nitronone **N1** and methyl crotonate **D2** has been shown in Scheme 12. The energy profile has been provided in Scheme 13.

The comparable magnitudes of bond orders indicate concerted mechanism with asynchronous transition states. However, the bond orders indicated a change of asynchronicity on the bond formation process for the two regioisomeric pathways. The *meta* transition states showed lower activation energies than *ortho* transition states. The stereoselectivity along the *ortho* channel was poor. On the contrary, along the *meta* pathway, the *endo* path presented fairly low activation energy compared to the corresponding *exo* channel. These results were in complete agreement with the experiments.

DFT/B3LYP/6-31G(d) optimized *meta* transition states for the *endo* and *exo* approach of benzylidene acetophenone (**D1**) over *C*-(4-chlorophenyl)-*N*-phenyl nitronone (**N2**) and *C*-(4-chlorophenyl)-*N*-methyl nitronone (**N3**) are shown in Scheme 13 as reported in our recent communication³⁹. The cycloaddition between **D1** and **N3** is favoured in the *endo*-reaction channel, being stabilised through an activation energy difference of 1.52 kcal mol⁻¹ over the *exo*-channel. This is in concordance with the experimentally evaluated diastereomeric ratio of 87 : 13 (Table 1). Computational results showed that replacement of *N*-phenyl group in **N2** by *N*-methyl in **N3** brings about a much greater destabilisation of the *exo* carbonyl approach compared to the *endo* attack.

We further reported⁵⁷ DFT studies for the cycloaddition reaction of a cyclic nitronone 1-pyrroline-1-oxide (**N4**) to benzylidene acetophenone (**D1**) and methyl cinnamate

Scheme 12. DFT/B3LYP/6-31G(d) optimized transition states for the reaction between *C,N*-diphenyl nitron (N1) and methyl crotonate (D2). The partial bond order values are in parenthesis after the forming bond lengths (in Å).

Scheme 13. Energy profile in kcal mol⁻¹ for the cycloaddition reaction between *C,N*-diphenyl nitron (N1) and methyl crotonate (D2).

(D3) The *endo* and *exo* transition states along the *meta* channel for the reaction between N4 and D1 are shown in Scheme 14. The reaction between N4 and D1 was calculated to be *exo* selective by 1 255 kcal mol⁻¹. However, for the reaction between N4 and D3, the *endo* transition state showed lower activation energy than the correspond-

ing *exo* approach by 1 882 kcal mol⁻¹. We observed that the functional group alteration from COPh in D1 to COOMe in D3 resulted in weak destabilization of *exo* channel and a simultaneous large destabilization of the *endo* channel. We reported in our earlier experimental findings for the reaction between N1 and 1-cinnamoyl

Scheme 14. DFT/B3LYP/6-31G(d) optimized transition states for the reactions of C(4-chlorophenyl)N-phenyl nitron (N2) and C(4-chlorophenyl)N-methyl nitron (N3) to benzylidene acetophenone (D1). The bond orders are in parenthesis after the forming bond lengths (in Å).

Scheme 15. DFT/B3LYP/6-31G(d) optimized transition states for the reaction of 1-pyrroline 1-oxide (N4) to benzylidene acetophenone (D1). The bond orders are in parenthesis after the forming bond lengths (in Å).

piperidine that the reaction path was *endo*-selective^{52,53}. Thus, it could be anticipated that for reactions with N1, the amide carbonyl or ester carbonyl substituent on the dipolarophiles effectively diverts the diastereofacial mode of attack in comparison to the keto phenyl moiety.

DFT study of 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition reactions of cyclic nitron to α,β -unsaturated lactones and with cyclic vinyl ethers has been recently reported¹³⁷.

Theoretical study of catalysed 1,3-dipolar cycloadditions remain a less investigated aspects of these reactions. The uncatalyzed and Lewis acid mediated cycloaddition reaction of *C*-phenyl-*N*-methyl nitron to cinnamionitrile has been recently reported by Wagner *et al.*¹³⁸. BF₃ was selected as the model for theoretical studies. The authors have reported that the selection of the computational level was crucial. High level methods like MP3 or MP4 were required to achieve convergent results. Basis set dependence was negligible : the results from 6-31G(d) calculations were in good agreement with the ones obtained with 6-311 + +G(d,p) basis set. Theoretical study of 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition reactions of allyl-anion type 1,3-dipoles to acrylonitrile – both free and coordinated to Pt^{II} and Pt^{IV} in the complexes *trans* [PtCl_n(NCMe)₂] (n = 2, 4) has been recently reported¹³⁹. The authors have reported that the reactivity increases along the following sequence of dipoles, the first three being inert toward nitriles; nitro compounds [ON(Me)O] < azoxy compounds [NHN(Me)O] < azimines [NHN(Me)NH] < nitrones [CH₂N(Me)O] < ozone [OOO] \approx nitrosimines [NHONH] < azomethine imines [CH₂N(Me)NH] < nitrosoxides [NHOO] < azomethine ylides [CH₂N(Me)CH₂] < carbonyl ylides [CH₂OCH₂] \approx carbonyl imines [CH₂ONH] < carbonyl oxides [CH₂OO].

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